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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Review Article****INFLUENCE OF STAFF' COMMUNICATIVE ABILITIES INTO
THE ENTERPRISE PERFORMANCE**Elvira Kutsova¹¹Institute of service and business (the branch) Don state technical university, Shakhty, Russia**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

This article reveals the features of communicative competences in the personnel management system of Russian companies. The article shows the role of internal communications in the company, the use of the term "competence", the content of communicative competence of staff. The areas of industrial practice are defined where the communicative competence of the communicative leader-leader is necessary, a number of blocks that diagnose possession of the theoretical, tactical and practical bases of communication are highlighted.

Keywords: communication, communication, competence, staff, manager

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INTRODUCTION:

According to M.Kh. Mescon, communication is the process of exchanging information between two or more people. Since an organization is a structured type of relations between people, ensuring the effective functioning of an organization largely depends on the quality of communications 1. This is obvious, because if communications between people are not effective, people simply cannot agree on a common goal. Information in the communication process is transmitted not only so that timely and informed decisions can be made that are consistent with the strategic objectives, but also so that decisions can be implemented. If the management of the organization can organize the movement of information in the structure from itself to its subordinates, then there is a chance of success. And as long as employees do not understand the goals and objectives of the organization, do not understand their direct responsibilities, and are not fully included in the organization's workflow, they cannot work well and be sufficiently motivated.

A well-established system of internal communications makes the company more manageable, and thus reduces costs. We are talking about costs that are often difficult to calculate: a reduction in the period of adaptation of new employees and their exit to "self-sufficiency", a decrease in resistance to changes, a reduction in the escalation of decisions made. An effective communication system allows you to establish transparency in the relationship between the management of the company, the broadcast goals of the organization and professionals, including those working with clients. As a result - high manageability of the company, responsive response to the changing market situation, higher quality customer service, increased staff motivation, involvement in the management of the organization. With the construction of a system of internal communications, a unified system of values, a common language and standards of work are created, which is especially important for large companies, especially for those who have a large branch network. Therefore, any organization is simply obliged to single out internal communications into an independent activity.

In modern socio-economic conditions, the nature of relationships has changed significantly, both within organizations and organizations with the external environment. There is a tendency to increase the burden on human resources, to the intensity and complexity of interpersonal communications, both directly and indirectly by various technical means,

increasing the requirements for the communicative competence of individuals and entire professional groups. The main mechanism capable of bridging the gap between the requirements of the market and the potential of the organization is the development of the communication skills of the company. One of the key points is the problem of professional readiness of the managerial staff of the organization and the priority is the development of the communicative competence of this category of employees.

The term "competence" has a professional and technological purpose. It is used when talking about the skills of an activity, certain skills, as well as a set of functional powers, rights and duties (provided by law, statute or other act to a specific body or official).

Competence embodies a set of ways to "rationalize" the activities of subjects in order to achieve on a communicative basis, streamlining (agreement) of their relationship with the existing conditions of functioning and development of social systems. Competence is communicative in nature. Thus, it turns out that the communicative nature of competence is clearly manifested in the process of social management.

Communicative competence involves the ability to communicate through language, that is, to transmit thoughts and exchange them in different situations in the process of interaction with other participants in communication, correctly using a system of language and speech norms and choosing communicative behavior that is adequate to the authentic communication situation. This also includes mastering the technique of questioning and answering them. Communicative competence is not a personal characteristic of a person; its formation is manifested in the process of professional communication. Business executives and professionals are increasingly using communication in business partnerships. Speaking about the concept of "communicative competence", it is worthwhile to dwell on the abilities and skills that it includes.

The communicative competence of the personnel began to acquire a particularly important role in the conditions of the knowledge economy, and for the head of the organization, possession of communicative competence in the conditions of the knowledge economy became insufficient for his professional activity. If a manager wants to achieve high results for his organization, he must assume the responsibility to comply with the role of a

“communicative leader”, i.e. personality, which has certain individual properties and characteristics (sociability, charisma, etc.), ensuring its constant high ability to choose the scheme of presentation and transmission of information in a particular production situation and adequately perceive information of various types.

G. Bakirova focuses on areas of work practice where the communicative competence of a manager is unconditional.

Firstly, when applying for a job, in order to achieve the goals of this line of activity of a manager, it is necessary at least to inform the potential employee about the enterprise, namely: its location, size, production capabilities, competition, financial situation, domestic policy, organizational structure, about the position for which the employee is selected, about his prospects, etc.

At the same time, it is necessary to find out as much as possible about the applicant in order to establish the extent to which he meets the requirements for a vacant position.

Secondly, the communicative competence of the head is very important in the adaptation of staff. In this case, the goal of the manager is to form a sense of confidence in the employee, a sense of organization as his own, not a stranger. To do this: the “newcomer” is introduced to colleagues, managers and subordinates; explain the policy and philosophy of the organization; report on the procedures, working conditions, mode of operation; show the main divisions, premises, etc.

If the listed tasks are not performed well enough, the “newcomer” can retire very soon, and this becomes a problem if he is a qualified and necessary employee for the organization. Thirdly, the communicative competence of the head is a necessary condition for the distribution of information within the organization. To do this, the organization’s personnel need: timely, undistorted, reliable information, which is usually transmitted in the communication process through one of the possible channels. In addition, the employee needs information about his role in the organization, how he copes with the tasks. And finally, individual staff assessment is also an area where communicative competence is indispensable, since this is one of the

important areas in human resource management. In order for the evaluation process not to turn into an opportunity to criticize workers once again, it is important to teach managers to do it correctly: so that after a conversation with employees, the motivation to work increases, rather than diminishes. Thus, the assessment is also carried out in the process of communication of the manager with subordinates. And the quality of this communication is very important for solving many issues, and most importantly - for the formation of motivation to work better and to achieve job satisfaction for employees.

A manager, using communicative competence, sets strategic and tactical communicative goals, defining a communicative perspective, i.e. the ability to bring about the desired effects in reality. Next, the head develops a communicative strategy that includes knowledge about his subordinates (their characteristics of character, behavior, motives, abilities, capabilities, etc.). This strategy is transformed into a communicative tactic that includes the knowledge, understanding and awareness of the methods of communication, the impact on a group of subordinates to achieve the goals of the organization. With its help, the manager has an impact on his team, enriching the skills and knowledge of subordinates.

The result of such a communicative tactic may be positive or negative, therefore one of the important goals of a manager is to evaluate it, i.e. awareness and analysis of the impact of this tactic, the methods of communication used on an individual subordinate and the team as a whole. This enriches the communicative experience of the leader and allows you to use or, on the contrary, avoid specific communicative tactics in your management activities.

Thus, due to the fact that the value of communicative competence in a knowledge economy is a necessary and indispensable condition, the question arises of its assessment. Today there are a sufficient number of different methods that in one way or another diagnose sociability, communication skills, communication tactics, etc. However, all these techniques should be reduced to a single monitoring, which will include a number of blocks that diagnose the possession of theoretical, tactical and practical bases of communication (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Analysis and evaluation of the communicative competence of staff

In the first block, “Analysis and Evaluation of a Theoretical Communication Base”, it is advisable to analyze and evaluate:

- features of verbal and non-verbal behavior in the communication process;
- types of interaction in the communication process; features of the influence of subjective interests, psychological state of a person, his experience, expectations from the process of communication; using or ignoring emotions in communication;
- structure and functions of the communicative act; structure, phases and tasks of dialogue, etc.

In the second block, “Analysis and Evaluation of Communication Techniques,” it is necessary to analyze and evaluate:

- active and passive listening;
- synchronization technique, that is, taking into account the status and behavior of the interlocutor; various dialogue strategies; the technique of resolving the differences of the interlocutors (explain the meaning, describe the rules and conditions of use, give a sample); techniques for relieving emotional stress;
- question technique; interpretation technique; pause technique; phased consent technique, etc.

The third block “Analysis and evaluation of practical communication base” should include analysis and evaluation:

- the ability to take the initiative to begin the dialogue and its conduct; the ability to understand the psychological characteristics of the interlocutor, to determine the congruence of his behavior, his desire or unwillingness to continue the conversation, his ability (willingness) to change his position, etc. ;
- in the presence or occurrence of emotional stress that interferes with the dialogue - the ability to align it without reducing the pace and efficiency of the conversation;

- when convincing a person - the ability to find out his position and attitude to the topic, goals, circumstances and other aspects of the conversation;
- the ability to give the interlocutor feedback on all aspects of the conversation;
- the ability to adjust the behavior of the interlocutor;
- ability to achieve the planned goal of the dialogue;
- ability to act as an arbitrator between the conflicting parties;
- ability to understand their requirements;
- the ability to find a constructive line of interaction between all parties;
- ability to manage the course of the dialogue and finish it at the right time, etc.

The content of communicative competence in the personnel management system of Russian companies depends on their professional orientation. First of all, we are talking about the knowledge of the personnel managers of the state of affairs in the field of public prestige, the image of the enterprise. This knowledge is largely due not only to the purposeful activities of image formation, but also with the history of the enterprise, as well as the experience of working on it as a manager. Patriarchal managers are more confident that they know well the image of how high the prestige of their enterprise. At the same time, among rational bureaucrats and manager-managers there is not one who is not informed about the image of their enterprise.

CONCLUSION:

The most priority areas for improving the efficiency of modern HR managers in the context of transforming managerial relations are:

1. Adaptation of Western technologies to Russian conditions. We are talking about the development of these technologies, when the possibility of their most complete implementation in the real practice of modern Russian enterprises is being formed. In the most complete form, rational bureaucrats insist on this direction of increasing the managerial competence of managers in modern Russia. They think somewhat more often than other groups of managers that normatively Western management technologies do not fit into modern Russian management.
2. Overcoming non-professionalism, increasing the level of managerial skill and competence of managers. This direction, in our opinion, involves primarily the formation and development of a system of professional training and retraining of managers. Especially often managers and managers need this direction, and not patriarchal managers

and rational bureaucrats. Therefore, they insist to a greater degree on the need to create a special system of professional education for managers at the expense of enterprises.

3. Raising the level of awareness of the team, enterprise, organization. We are talking about the development of a faster system, in a short time, the inclusion of the manager in the life activity of employees, understanding of the organization's mission. Of course, a lot here depends on the manager himself, his sociability, skills and abilities to promptly join the system of public relations and communications. Managers and managers also insist on the need to create conditions for rapid inclusion in the team.

4. Increasing the prospects for growth, further steady development of the enterprise. The need for this direction is more oriented managers of the patriarchal type. They are more aware of the need for this kind of direction to improve efficiency.

5. Approximately equally and mainly, managers-managers see as significant ways of increasing the effectiveness of the work of managers overcoming subjectivity in evaluating their activities and ensuring the interests of their subordinates on the part of their supervisors.

6. Patriarchal managers are more inclined to destroy the old schemes of management. Rational bureaucrats with such a direction to improve the managerial competence of managers do not agree, and most managers-managers doubt it.

7. Increasing the material interest of managers in a more successful work and a more decent salary were not so significant in general for managers. For example, rational bureaucrats and managers-managers did not allocate it at all. Only patriarchal managers are convinced of the need to change for the better the increase in revenues.

8. The rational bureaucrats are no longer satisfied with the state system of support for the professionalization of management. Patriarchal bureaucrats generally believe more often that managers are not needed in Russia. The main reason is considered in the market of educational services the need for managerial specialties, the unwillingness of employers to provide future managers with places for work experience. Therefore, today there is a need for the development of the process of professionalization of Russian management in all its manifestations, starting with the definition of managerial qualities of future managers, and completing the system of development of their acquired professional knowledge and skills.

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